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CONTACTS

Phone: **97-748-70-03**

Website: <https://ist-journal.uz>

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RESTRUCTURING OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

B. Sulaymonov

PhD, Associate Professor of
the Department of "Trade business"
Tashkent State Economic University
ORCID: 0009-0002-4838-1124

Abstract: The article examines the practical aspects of restructuring industrial enterprises. It analyzes the factors and reasons that drive the restructuring process in industrial enterprises in Uzbekistan. Additionally, it explores the characteristics of foreign experience in restructuring industrial sectors in other countries.

Key words: restructuring, complex changes, enterprises, adaptation, industry, sector, industrial products, external and internal environment.

INTRODUCTION

Restructuring is a complex process of implementing significant changes in the functional activities of an enterprise. Its primary goal is to adapt to shifts in both the external and internal environment while enhancing business competitiveness. The key elements in this definition are the external and internal environment, as they have a profound impact on any commercial organization. Accordingly, enterprise restructuring is planned based on past changes as well as anticipated future developments.

A critical question arises: What factors and triggers play the most significant role in influencing the restructuring of an industrial enterprise? Analyzing these factors will help identify the key triggers and trends that drive the necessity for industrial enterprise management to undertake restructuring.

Industrial enterprises in Uzbekistan face intense competition and rapidly evolving business conditions. Without substantial reorganization and restructuring, their survival is at risk. Restructuring can be broadly defined as the efficient utilization of production resources capital, labor, land, and entrepreneurial abilities—to enhance business value. In developed countries, enterprise restructuring is widespread, progressing at an accelerated pace with increasingly refined implementation methods. Continuous restructuring is essential for business survival in a dynamic external environment. The success of restructuring largely depends on the chosen methodology and the consistency of its implementation, particularly in relation to customers, suppliers, and regulatory authorities.

Below are descriptions of various approaches used in restructuring Western and domestic enterprises. The first classification criterion is the type of restructuring management, which may be based on: regulation, formal control, or order; creativity and the development of organizational culture. A formalized approach is often justified when restructuring crisis enterprises. In such cases, bankruptcy legislation provides a framework within which crisis managers and consulting teams must operate to either restore viability or liquidate the enterprise. In Western enterprises, restructuring is commonly based on business units, key competencies, resource-based approaches, and minimalist strategies. Currently, foreign enterprise owners increasingly rely on a behavioral management approach. However, transitioning from rigid management methods to liberal ones has taken decades. For instance, American managers required over three decades for this shift, while Japanese managers completed it in approximately two decades. In contrast, domestic enterprises face challenges in adopting the behavioral approach due to a high proportion of unprofitable firms, the persistence of a traditional management mentality, and employees' lack of experience in working under liberal management conditions.

Experts from the Russian Privatization Center recommend business unit-based restructuring for domestic enterprises. This approach focuses on decentralization and the creation of strategic business units (SBUs). Each SBU functions as an independent production and commercial entity, fostering the development of skills and expertise for a more agile response to changes in internal and external environments.

However, department heads often prioritize internal process optimization, which may hinder the implementation of hybrid restructuring strategies. This lack of coordination can reduce synergy between departments and limit the effective transfer of talented specialists. To achieve a truly effective restructuring model, enterprises must integrate mechanisms that promote cross-departmental collaboration and innovation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The restructuring process is a complex tool aimed at achieving competitiveness and strategic advantages. A one-sided understanding of restructuring may lead to limitations in utilizing its full potential.

Leading economists in the field of anti-crisis management, particularly in restructuring, argue that it is a fundamental and long-term process. For instance, CIS scientists I.I. Mazur and V.D. Shapiro define restructuring as “a set of measures to ensure the adaptation of an enterprise to changing market conditions and its development strategy” [2].

G.A. Aleksandrov emphasizes the fundamental and comprehensive nature of restructuring. He describes it as “a fundamental and complex transformation of the business structure that encompasses all aspects of the enterprise and its main objectives. The ultimate goal of restructuring is to overcome crises, improve efficiency and competitiveness, and increase income” [3].

L.P. Belykh and M.A. Fedotova outline the key objectives of enterprise restructuring. They state that “restructuring is a process aimed at creating conditions for the effective use of all factors of production to enhance financial stability and competitiveness” [4].

Sukharev provides a more extensive description of restructuring, highlighting the pivotal role of state policy in the process. According to him, “restructuring is applied at the levels of enterprises, regions, and entire sectors of the economy, leading to the formation of state-controlled competitiveness, employment growth, real income expansion, and increased investment in industrial complexes. It also involves a set of measures sufficient to ensure competitive pressure from both domestic and foreign competitors” [5].

The need for restructuring arises due to intensified competition resulting from the development of productive forces and evolving market conditions. In this context, Yaushev’s definition sheds light on the economic essence of restructuring: “Restructuring is a set of measures aimed at selecting an enterprise development strategy and facilitating the transition from its initial state to the chosen strategic direction” [6].

G. Hamer introduced the concept of restructuring based on core competencies. Core competencies refer to unique technologies, well-established high-quality production processes, and highly skilled personnel. The key principle of this method is the identification, development, and application of technological potential. A specific example of a core competency model is the outsourcing model. However, the application of core competency and outsourcing models in Uzbekistan is challenging due to the financial instability of many enterprises, low technological capacity, and the absence of dedicated R&D departments.

The resource-based approach, proposed by S. Deju, P. Baldi, and J. Morei, is founded on the strategic concept of management, which strengthens an enterprise’s competitive position. This approach primarily involves identifying organizational competencies, determining strategic growth areas within an enterprise, and reinforcing these areas based on an accumulated “portfolio of strategic competencies.” This management approach can be applied in the restructuring of both successful enterprises and those experiencing financial difficulties. Additionally, it can be integrated with other approaches, such as business unit creation and minimalism, to address crises effectively.

Harvard Business School and the consulting firm Arthur D. Little developed the concept of minimalism in restructuring. The core idea of this approach is to eliminate all unnecessary elements in the production process, including excessive costs, time losses, defects, bottlenecks, and surplus inventory. A key principle of minimalism is the economic and financial evaluation of internal production parameters. The application of this approach in Uzbekistan holds promise, as price competition remains viable only until an enterprise exhausts its cost-cutting reserves. Without effective restructuring, prolonged cost reduction efforts may lead to declining profit margins, financial deterioration, and, ultimately, business failure.

Restructuring methodologies developed by foreign scholars and extensively tested in Western economies are also being implemented in Uzbekistan. However, the unique characteristics of the domestic economy necessitate the development of original restructuring frameworks tailored to local conditions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This article examines the management of restructuring processes in industrial enterprises. Various methods, such as the verbal interpretation of scientific and theoretical foundations, statistical observation, induction and deduction, and scientific abstraction, were utilized.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

One of the most common restructuring schemes in enterprises is bankruptcy, which is often fictitious. The primary causes of illegal bankruptcy include deliberate criminal actions aimed at writing off debts, changing the ownership of the enterprise, concealing income, evading taxes, and withdrawing the most liquid assets at a price below their residual book value. Given these challenges, the legal framework governing the restructuring processes of domestic enterprises requires significant revision.

In the Uzbek market, one prevalent restructuring method involves the creation of new subsidiaries based on production units, to which the highest quality and most liquid assets are transferred. This approach can partially stimulate internal production reserves and does not require creditor approval. However, transferring high-quality assets without analyzing the root causes of insolvency will inevitably lead to another liquidity crisis. As a result, the newly created subsidiary may eventually need to establish additional firms to sustain its operations.

One of the major challenges in the current restructuring landscape is the absence of well-defined theoretical and applied methods. In domestic practice, there is no established mechanism for determining when an enterprise requires restructuring, which prevents managers from initiating timely reengineering efforts. Existing methodologies fail to outline the sequence of actions during restructuring and do not provide a comprehensive framework for selecting the appropriate type and strategy based on the enterprise's condition. Additionally, there is no systematic approach to evaluating restructuring effectiveness, nor is there a structured methodology for financial recovery. The absence of a clear program and algorithm for enterprise restructuring further exacerbates these challenges. Therefore, developing a universal methodology for enterprise restructuring is imperative. Such a framework should include mechanisms for assessing the feasibility of restructuring and for selecting the most suitable method and strategy.

A well-structured concept would help coordinate the actions of all stakeholders in the restructuring process, including managers, creditors, and investors, while ensuring tangible support from banks and shareholders. Without a properly planned restructuring strategy, enterprises may struggle to sustain long-term growth and enhance their competitive position in the market.

The external economic environment plays a crucial role in the restructuring process, as does the interaction between industrial enterprises and various stakeholders, including business owners, managers, personnel, creditors, and consumers. However, not all external factors are within the control of even the largest industrial corporations. In such cases, adaptation to changing market conditions becomes the only viable option, which is often the primary reason for initiating restructuring.

Regarding internal changes, management decisions have a substantial impact. Industrial enterprise managers have access to numerous tools and models for optimizing internal processes, ultimately enhancing operational efficiency and ensuring successful restructuring outcomes. However, in Uzbekistan, restructuring management practices in the industrial sector are not always effective. Learning from the experiences of industrialized economies may provide valuable insights.

In countries with developed market economies, restructuring is considered an essential tool within the framework of a naturally evolving market process. The application of best practices from these economies could significantly enhance the restructuring strategies of Uzbek industrial enterprises.

Western models of restructuring are a reflection of changes in the market environment and competition. Under these conditions, the restructuring of an industrial enterprise is usually equivalent to diversification, which the company carries out in the context of established legal norms and rules of economic behavior. In most developed countries, the restructuring of industrial companies is regulated by the legislative and regulatory framework adopted at the state level [1].

Foreign experience in restructuring industrial enterprises includes government programs and policies aimed at structural changes within the industry and stimulating the growth of production activity. For Uzbekistan, the most valuable is the experience of restructuring the industrial sector of China, which occupies a leading place in the structure of the world economy. Thus, within the framework of the state program, the following stages of restructuring industrial enterprises were observed [7]:

Pre-reform stage, during which the Chinese government purchased foreign technologies and scientific developments for local industrial enterprises.

Experimental stage, during which local industrial enterprises began to independently purchase the necessary scientific developments, patents, licenses, technologies, and innovations.

Stage of structural reforms, during which the Chinese government allocated budget expenditures for financing scientific and technological developments, technology parks, business incubators, etc.

Stage of growth of science intensity of products, during which the privatization of industrial enterprises took place, and foreign financing was attracted for the formation of R&D.

Stage of strengthening innovation activity, during which the state financed the sphere of education and science and created conditions for the external environment to form world-class scientific developments and leading positions for China's industrial enterprises.

If we turn to the progressive experience of other foreign countries, it is necessary to note examples of successful restructuring of industrial enterprises in the USA and Germany, as they were able to attract financing from large foreign investors during the privatization process. The main factors for the effective implementation of restructuring in the industrial sectors of Western countries include a well-developed stock market and strong financial support from the state for individual sectors of the economy [8].

Analyzing the experience of German industry, it is worth noting that the privatization process took place before the reorganization, modernization, and restructuring of enterprises. The successful restructuring of the US industry was carried out by placing shares of enterprises on the stock market. After attracting funds, illiquid and unprofitable production assets were sold, while those that functioned successfully attracted additional financial, labor, and intellectual resources. Thus, foreign experience in restructuring industrial enterprises demonstrates a successful model in which mutually beneficial cooperation is formed between the state and the corporate sector. The state plays a key role in stimulating the scientific activity of enterprises, forming an education system, and developing technology parks, business incubators, accelerators, etc. The corporate sector, in turn, attracts large-scale financing for industrial projects, facilitating the restructuring of industrial enterprises to modernize assets, implement new technologies, and produce innovative products.

The practical implementation of the restructuring concept should lead to sustainable positive short-term and long-term changes in the enterprise's operations, ultimately increasing the market value of its equity capital and ordinary shares. The scope of the restructuring process depends on whether it involves operational restructuring focused on addressing immediate economic and financial challenges—or a more complex stage of strategic restructuring.

The primary goal of operational restructuring is to enhance the enterprise's short-term performance while creating the foundation for strategic restructuring. This process primarily involves restructuring tangible assets and debt obligations. The outcome of operational restructuring is an improvement in the liquidity of the enterprise's assets, achieved through inventory reduction, a decrease in accounts receivable, and the sale of surplus assets. Additionally, operational restructuring entails adjustments in the structure of attracted capital. When managed effectively, these changes contribute to a higher return on equity and, consequently, the restoration of solvency alongside improved profitability.

A strategic restructuring program should outline well-defined objectives, directions, decision-making criteria, and implementation steps. This includes analyzing the enterprise's business areas, establishing an efficient information system, conducting marketing research, and formulating marketing and sales strategies. It also involves developing a procurement strategy for raw materials and exploring potential growth options. The successful execution of strategic restructuring results in an increased net present value of future income, enhanced long-term competitiveness, and a higher market value of the enterprise's equity—making it more attractive to investors.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

When considering enterprise restructuring strategies, it is advisable to explore options that require minimal capital investment and external financing, as well as investment projects for the complete re-equipment of production. However, for many domestic enterprises, the primary objective of restructuring is to satisfy creditors' demands an approach that is not always aligned with the traditional goal of restructuring, which is to enhance the company's value.

During a structural crisis, the choice of a restructuring concept may be constrained to low-risk strategies, particularly when the business value is at or near zero. In such cases, implementing a cluster model of restructuring can be an effective solution. This model serves as a defensive mechanism designed to ensure an organization's survival under crisis conditions. A similar approach is used in Western economies as part of an anti-crisis "compression" strategy, which focuses on consolidating raw material suppliers in close proximity to the core production facility. This restructuring method minimizes the scale of main production while ensuring operational efficiency.

One key aspect of this approach is the optimization of the product range. By reducing the number of market offerings, enterprises retain only their most competitive and in-demand products. This streamlining process leads to the liquidation of non-essential assets and the release of production space, which can then be repurposed or monetized to generate additional revenue.

For Uzbekistan's enterprises, the traditional functional approach to management and restructuring should be replaced with a process-oriented approach. Unlike the functional model, which focuses on the independent

functions of various structural divisions, the process approach prioritizes end-to-end business processes that span multiple divisions. This holistic perspective ensures greater efficiency, flexibility, and responsiveness to market dynamics, ultimately improving enterprise performance in an evolving business environment.

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